

White Topping Overlay for Rehabilitation of Bituminous Roads

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ABSTRACT

Concrete overlays have been used to rehabilitate both the existing bituminous (flexible) pavement since 1918 and existing concrete pavement since 1913. Whitetopping in its various forms have been used in the USA and Europe on Airports, Inter-state roads, Primary & Secondary Highways, Local Roads, Streets and Parking lots to improve the performance, durability and riding quality of deteriorated bituminous pavement surfaces. There has been a renewed interest in whitetopping, particularly, in Thin & Ultra Thin Whitetopping during the last decade. This has been possible due to several successful high profile projects executed in USA and Europe. Their effectiveness has further renewed interest in them because they satisfy the demand caused by rapidly deteriorating highways confronted with limited fund availability. Whitetopping of all types, viz; Conventional Whitetopping, Thin Whitetopping (TWT) and Ultra Thin Whitetopping (UTWT) offer immense potential as a rehabilitation strategy for Indian roads. Several successful projects have been executed at Pune, Mumbai, Delhi, Nagpur, Jaipur and Bangalore in the last few years. The performance of these sections has been found to be satisfactory. The paper discusses the design and construction aspects of TWT.

1. INTRODUCTION

Concrete is a very durable material for the construction of roads and highways. Cement concrete has been used for the construction of new roads, highways and also for the rehabilitation of existing distressed bituminous pavements.

Several highways, expressway and city roads have been constructed with cement concrete in the recent past in India. Cement concrete roads offer long life of more than 30 years and minimum maintenance requirement. Rutting of bituminous pavement is a real problem in hot climate like India, with heavy truck loads, operating under frequent start/stop conditions. It is commonly applied where rutting of bituminous pavements is a recurring problem. Concrete overlays offer the potential for extended service life, increased structural and functional capacity, reduced maintenance requirements, and lower life-cycle costs when compared with bituminous overlay alternative.

Concrete overlays have been used to rehabilitate both the existing bituminous (flexible) pavement since 1918 and existing concrete pavement since 1913. Whitetopping in its various forms have been used in the USA and Europe on Airports, Inter-state roads, Primary & Secondary Highways, Local Roads, Streets and Parking lots to improve the performance, durability and riding quality of deteriorated bituminous pavement surfaces. There has been a renewed interest in whitetopping, particularly, in Thin & Ultra Thin Whitetopping during the last decade. This has been possible due to several successful high profile projects executed in USA and Europe. Their effectiveness has further renewed interest in them because they satisfy the

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2. WHITETOPPING

Whitetopping is defined as a Portland Cement Concrete (PCC) overlay constructed on the top of an existing bituminous pavement. Whitetopping is thus PCC resurfacing (overlay) as a rehabilitation or structural strengthening alternative on bituminous pavement. The PCC overlay may or may not be bonded to the layer below. Whitetopping involves placing a concrete overlay on a distressed bituminous pavement.

3. ADVANTAGES OF WHITETOPPING

Whitetopping on existing bituminous pavements provides many additional benefits as compared to conventional bituminous overlay alternative. Some of the benefits are:

- Long life, low maintenance, low life-cycle cost, improved safety and environmental benefits.
- Bituminous overlays exhibit a more rapid loss of serviceability as compared to concrete whitetopping at some critical locations. The lives of successive bituminous overlays become progressively shorter after the first overlay.
- Deformation like rutting and cracking predominant in case of bituminous pavements is normally absent with concrete surfaces of whitetopping. This is particularly true in a hot climate like India.
- Conventional Whitetopping improves structural capacity of existing bituminous pavement, if built on a strong base course, and it impedes structural distresses.
- Whitetopping requires much less maintenance and as such involves much less frequent lane closures of road, as compared to bituminous surfaces.
- Whitetopping is quite cost-effective to tackle annual budget constraints and high traffic levels. It is, therefore, quite relevant to Indian conditions.
- Whitetopping can uniformly fill ruts in the wheel path of bituminous pavements more effectively because concrete is far more stiff and consistent at high temperature than bituminous mixes. Broadly, for similar reasons, the occurrence of cracks is also relatively much less in case of whitetopping.

- Concrete is relatively light in colour and hence concrete surface is more reflective to light, absorb less heat and reduce the urban heat island effect. Improved reflection of lights from vehicles enhances safety, lowers energy requirement of external lighting, lower contribution to heat in environment.
- Fuel consumption on concrete roads has been found to be less than the bituminous roads.

4. CATEGORIES OF WHITETOPPING

Depending upon the traffic, axle loads of the vehicles and thickness of the overlay, whitetopping is often categorized as Ultrathin Whitetopping (UTWT), Thin Whitetopping (TWT) and Conventional Whitetopping (CWT).

4.1 Ultrathin Whitetopping

UTWT typically involves placing 50 mm to 100 mm thick concrete overlay with joint spacing ranging from 1.0 m to 1.5 m. It is mainly used for the areas with very low volume of light traffic like two wheelers and cars as is normally observed on internal colony lanes. Bonding between underlying bituminous layer and overlaid PCC layer is mandatory in case of Ultra Thin Whitetopping. Milling the existing bituminous surface to an average depth of 25 mm is normally used to provide the bonding at the interface between the existing bituminous surface and PCC overlay. Milling not only removes the top deteriorated part of the bituminous layer but it also produce a rough surface which can develop some kind of bonding between the existing milled bituminous surface and concrete overlay. The bonding helps ultrathin concrete overlay to sustain traffic for a longer period.

4.2 Thin Whitetopping

TWT concrete overlay is 100 mm to 200 mm thick with the same joint spacing of 1.0 m to 1.5 m. The bond between the overlaid PCC and underlying bituminous layer is often a consideration but it is not mandatory. The bonding consideration may be ignored in the design.

4.3 Conventional Whitetopping

Conventional whitetopping is more than 200 mm thick with the joint spacing and slab size (3.5 m x 4.5 m) similar to concrete pavement. It is designed and constructed without consideration of any bond between the concrete overlay and underlying bituminous layer. Conventional whitetopping is designed as per the provisions of IRC:58 and constructed like a new rigid pavement without assuming any composite action. Conventional whitetopping treats the existing bituminous surface as a sub-base like Dry Lean Concrete (DLC) and to this extent the condition of existing bituminous surface does not matter significantly, except that bituminous surface should not suffer from any isolated damages like subsidence or material related problems.

5. DESIGN CONCEPT

A conventional concrete pavement is designed on the basis of flexural stresses which are induced in the concrete slab due to its bending under environmental and vehicular loads. These stresses depends to a large extent on the size of the slab i.e. its length and width. In a conventional concrete pavement slab of

size 3.5 m x 4.5 m, the load is predominantly resisted by bending of the slab and the role of compression is very less. But, the role of bending reduces and that of compression increases with reduction in the size of the slab. As the bending stresses reduce in the smaller size slab, the requirement of slab thickness also reduces. Thus, when we go for economical and thinner concrete pavements, the size of the concrete slabs is kept small.

In case of conventional concrete pavement adopted for highways carrying heavy truck traffic, the size of the slab is kept larger to reduce the number of transverse joints and, thus, reducing the cost of saw cutting, dowels and joint sealant. But, in case of city roads which carry mostly lighter city traffic, the provision of dowel bars as a load transfer system at all joints is not generally adopted. Thus, shorter concrete panels without any dowel bar system at transverse joints is adopted for designing the thinner and economical concrete overlays over existing bituminous roads. The panel size most commonly is kept as 1m x 1m which may go upto maximum size of 1.5m x 1.5m.

The curling of concrete slabs also depends on its size. Larger the panel, larger will be the curling effect. Since, dowels are not provided at transverse joints, the corners of the slabs are very much prone to cracking under combined action of curling and wheel load. Shorter panels, thus, will have lesser tendency of corner cracking. That is why mostly shorter panels of 1m x 1m are preferred for thin concrete pavement.

The predominant mode of structural failure of short panelled concrete pavement or whitetopping is corner failure and the present design concept of such pavement is base on the criteria of corner cracking. Current IRC guidelines for the design of thin whitetopping (IRC:SP:76-2015) are also based on the corner cracking as main mode of structural failure. Though other modes of failure like transverse and longitudinal cracking are also possible and with further gain in the knowledge of field performance of such pavements, the current corner-cracking based design concept may get modified in future. The important design features of white topping can be summarised as given below.

- Concrete panel size is kept small, generally between 1m x 1m and 1.5m x 1.5m to design a thinner and economical concrete pavement
- Dowel bars are not provided at saw cut transverse joints. Dowels are provided only at transverse construction joints which are full depth butt type of joints.
- Tie bars are not provided at saw cut longitudinal joints. Tie bars are provided only at longitudinal construction joints which are full depth butt type of joints
- Sealing of joints is not mandatory and generally not adopted.

6 CONSTRUCTION ASPECTS

Treatment of the surface of existing bituminous road is an important activity before placing cement concrete overlay over it. For conventional whitetopping wherein normal concrete panel size of 3.5m x 4.5m is designed, no special efforts are made to encourage bonding between the overlay and underlying bituminous surface. The concrete overlay is placed directly on the existing bituminous surface after cleaning it. Any depressions/rutting etc in the existing pavement are filled with concrete. Sometimes a levelling course of bituminous mix is used to produce a uniform surface for paving. A levelling course typically consists of minimum 50 mm of Bituminous Macadam (BM). Levelling/profile correction can also be done by using a 75mm to 125mm thick Dry Lean Concrete (DLC). Conventionally a separation layer in the form of 125 micron thick polythene sheet is used between DLC and concrete overlay.

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6.1 Milling of Bituminous Surface

Milling of top bituminous surface is often performed in case of thin and ultrathin whitetopping concrete overlays. Milling is done to remove surface distresses like cracking, ravelling, obtain a uniform surface with adjustment of cross slope and more importantly to get a rough surface which help develop the bond between left-out bituminous surface and concrete overlay. The rough surface obtain after milling help create a mechanical type of bonding between bituminous and concrete layers in which protruding aggregates of milled bituminous surface are interlocked with overlying concrete layer. The bond help in reducing the critical temperature and load stresses induced in the shorter and thinner concrete panels thereby making the concrete overlay perform better structurally. The thickness of milled out bituminous layer is generally between 25 to 50 mm. After milling the minimum thickness of the bituminous layer left behind must be 75 mm to get structural advantage of composite section formed due to bonding between bituminous and concrete layers. Photo 1 shows the milling of existing bituminous surface. Photo 2 shows the rough surface achieved after milling.

Photo 1. Milling of Bituminous Surface

Photo 2. Milled Rough Surface

6.2 Concrete Laying and Curing

Normal operation of concrete overlay construction involves mixing, placing, compaction, finishing and texturing. Concrete mix of required strength is designed and prepared in a concrete batching plant. Though, concrete mix of M40 Grade is used for whitetopping overlays, but concrete of higher strength like M45, M50 or M60 may also be used for early opening of the road to traffic within three to seven days. Concrete mix may be prepared in a batching plant erected at site or it can be procured from any ready mix concrete plant. Concrete laying, compaction and finishing operations can be done in manual semi mechanized method as well as using fixed or slip form concrete pavers. Since, slip form pavers require a bit extra width for its laying operations, therefore, such pavers may not be suitable for placing whitetopping overlays on city roads where extra width is not available. Fixed form paver can easily be used for compacting and finishing whitetopping overlays in city conditions. Fixed form paver consists of a number of vibrators which compact the concrete and a roller finisher which finishes the concrete surface while moving on fixed form work on both sides. Finished concrete is textured to get an anti-skid surface. Tine texturing in transverse direction is the most preferred way for city roads. Photo 3 shows laying concrete overlay using fixed form paver. Photo 4 shows the tine texturing operation.

Photo 3. Fixed Form Paving

Photo 4. Transverse Tine Texturing

6.3 Joints

After placing, finishing and texturing the concrete, initial saw cuts are made within 6-18 hours. Saw cutting should never be delayed beyond 24 hours after placement. Width of initial cut is kept 3-5 mm and saw cut depth should be 1/3 of the slab thickness. Both transverse and longitudinal saw cut are made at an interval of 1m to produce panels of 1m x 1m or as per the designed size.

Dowel bars are provided at all transverse construction butt joints. Plain mild steel dowels with plastic sheathing of 25 mm dia, 500 mm length may be provided at a spacing of 300 mm c/c. Photo 5 shows the dowels placed at transverse construction joint.

Tie bars are to be provided at all longitudinal construction joint to avoid the opening up of the joint which if not prevented may become a safety hazard for moving traffic. Deformed steel tie bars of length 500 mm, 10 mm dia may be provided at a spacing of 750 mm. Photo 5 shows the placement of tie bars at a longitudinal construction joint.

Photo 4. Doweled Transverse Construction Joint

Photo 5. Tied Longitudinal Construction Joint

Sealing of all transverse and longitudinal joint is optional. The initial saw cut of 3-5 mm width may be

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left unsealed or it can be sealed using a suitable sealant or preformed seals. If joints are decided to be sealed then there is no need of making a sealing groove by widening the initial saw cut. The panel size of whitetopping concrete overlays is very small (1 m x 1m) as compared to the size of conventional concrete pavement (3.5m x 4.5m), therefore the movements related to the expansion and contraction of the panels will be quite less and hence a wider sealing groove to accommodate the movement is not required. Thus, 3-5 mm width of the initial cut itself can be sealed if required. Sealing with bituminous sealant should be avoided. Though such sealants are cheap but may melt out of the joint initially and become hard and cracked within 1-2 years. Photo 6 shows unsealed joints and Photo 7 shows bituminous sealant melted out of the joints.

Photo 6. Unsealed Joints

Photo 7. Joints Sealed with Bituminous Sealant

7. COST ASPECTS

Most often, the rehabilitation strategy for city roads is to either overlay with both Dense Bitumen Macadam (DBM) as strengthening layer along with Bituminous Concrete (BC) as wearing layer or overlay with only BC layer. Another alternate rehabilitation strategy could be whitetopping with cement concrete overlay. Thus, the three rehabilitation strategies for the existing bituminous city roads are:

- (i) Overlay of 40 mm thick BC
- (ii) Overlay of 75 mm DBM + 40 mm BC
- (iii) Whitetopping with concrete overlay

The cost of different overlays has been calculated as per current cost of materials and given below.

ITEM	Cost, Rs.
Bituminous Concrete	10000/Cu.m
Dense Bitumen Macadam	9500/Cu.m
M40 Grade Concrete	6000/Cu.m
40 mm Thick BC	400/Sq.m
75 mm Thick DBM	712/Sq.m
10 cm Thick M40 Grade PCC	600/Sq.m
15 cm Thick M40 Grade PCC	900/sq.m
20 cm Thick M40 Grade PCC	1200/sq.m

If 40 mm BC overlay is adopted as a rehabilitation measure, then in a period of 25 years, it has to be

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repeated five times and the cost will be Rs.2000/Sq.m. On the other hand if 100 mm thick concrete overlay is adopted with its minimum life of 25 years, then its cost will be Rs.600/Sq.m. Thus, though initial cost of a bituminous overlay is less than the initial cost of a whitetopping overlay, but if costs are compared for a life of 25 years, then, whitetopping is much less expensive.

If a combination of 75 mm DBM and 40 mm BC is adopted for improving a city road, then total initial cost becomes Rs.1112/Sq.m which is more than the initial cost of even 150 mm thick whitetopping overlay.

Thus, it can be concluded that whitetopping overlay is a very cost effective rehabilitation and maintenance measure for city roads. Such overlays are designed for 25-30 years of design life but there actual service life may even be greater.

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